
THE GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ROMANTIC POETRY IN AMERICAN LITERATURE

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Abstract: This paper attempts to focus on American Romanticism in poetry, elucidating its key characteristics through notable works and poets. It investigates the movement's emphasis on individualism, awe of nature, idealization of women, celebration of the individual, break from convention, and spiritual inclinations. Through analysis and examples, it showcases how American Romanticism contributed to the shaping of the nation's literary identity during the 19th century. Through this paper we can innovate many new ideas and philosophies of the age of Romanticism.

Keywords: American Romanticism, poetry, characteristics, individualism, nature, idealization, rebellion, spirituality.

Introduction

The Romantic period in American literature stands as a pivotal moment in the nation's literary history, characterized by a profound shift in literary sensibilities and themes. Emerging in the aftermath of the American Revolution, this era was marked by a growing disillusionment with the rationalism and scientific progressivism of the Enlightenment. Instead, writers of the Romantic period sought to the depths of human emotion, the mysteries of nature, and the complexities of the individual psyche. American Romanticism is a frame of thought that places value on the individual above the group, the subjective response and instinct over objective thought, and emotion over logic. American Romanticism was the first real literary movement in the new nation and served to help define a society. Around the middle of the 1850s, as American literature was starting to take on its own identity, American Romanticism began to take shape. As the earliest recognized literary movement in American history, this movement has particular relevance for the country's history. Similar to other countries, the United States experienced the birth of Romanticism as a result of a desire to conserve the natural beauty of a pure, magnificent continent before its natural resources were destroyed or exploited beyond repair as a necessary part of the nation's capitalist economy. But aristocrats and artists also appropriated Romanticism to convey a sense of pride and superiority in America. Americans looked to the one thing the Continent lacked - the promise of an endless natural environment on a vast scale - to create a sense of patriotism for the emerging nation,

lacking the vast legacy of artistic and sociopolitical achievements that Europe appropriated for nationalistic pride. The somewhat earlier European Romantic movement had a significant influence on the American Romantic movement, although American writing differed from European Romanticism in its fundamental characteristics. American Romanticism is characterized by an emphasis on the individual, a love of the natural world, and the imagination. American Romanticism prioritized the individual over the collective. People came to America as the nation grew in order to make a life for themselves. An increase in immigration also brought about changes and increased diversity within the American community. The early Americans sought a more profound sense of self as a result of these two significant shifts. The urge to identify a national identity was central to much of the American Romantic literature, as many social groupings blended together to make one cohesive nation. A significant portion of American Romantic literature centered on the social outsider as a hero who lived on the periphery of society and according to their own set of rules. In American romanticism, the development of the “self” becomes a major theme “self-awareness” a primary method. If, according to Romantic theory, self and nature were one, self-awareness was not a selfish dead-end but a mode of knowledge opening up the universe. If one’s self were one with all humanity, then the individual had a moral duty to reform social inequalities and relieve human suffering. The idea of “self” which suggested selfishness to earlier generations—was redefined. New compound words with positive meaning emerged “self-realization”, “self-expression”, “self-reliance”⁶⁶.

American Romanticism was personal, intense and described more emotion than ever seen in other movements of literature. Preoccupation with freedom of America’s became an immense motivation for Romantic writers as many were encouraged about free expression and emotion without so much fear of ridicule and controversy. They put more attention and effort into the psychological development of their characters as well. The central characters typically portrayed extremes of sensitivity and excitement⁶⁷. Romanticism was affirmative and appropriate for most American poets and creative essayists. America’s vast mountains, deserts, and tropics embodied the sublime. The Romantic spirit seemed particularly suited to American democracy: it stressed individualism, affirmed the value of the common person, and looked to the inspired imagination for its aesthetic and ethical values. Certainly the New England Transcendentalists—

⁶⁶ Investigating American Romanticism: A Comparative Study Sabera Sultana, Md. Mohiul Islam OSR Journal Of Humanities And Social Science (IOSR-JHSS) Volume 21, Issue 4, Ver. 05 (Apr. 2016) PP 58-65

⁶⁷ Romanticism. American “ in the Oxford Dictionary of American Art and Artist ed. by Ann Morgan (Oxford University Press ,2007)

Ralph Waldo Emerson, Henry David Thoreau, and their associates—were inspired to a new optimistic affirmation by the Romantic Movement. In New England, Romanticism fell upon fertile soil.

During the Industrial Revolution, a time of progress for American society and of optimism, the ideology focused on the importance of ingenuity and the ability of the average person to succeed with hard work and creativity. The Romantic writers valued the power of imagination and wrote about it to escape overpopulated, polluted cities. For example, a poem, „There is no Frigate like a Book,, by Emily Dickinson emphasizes the importance of imagination in life:

*There is no Frigate like a Book
To take us Lands away
Nor any Coursers like a Page
Of prancing Poetry—*

*This Traverse may the poorest take
Without oppress of Tol—
How frugal is the Chariot
That bears the Human Soul—*

The poem vividly shows us Emily Dickinson’s awareness of the power of imagination to reveal the unseen truths in life. An attempt to escape from reality is clearly shown here, the writer shows the magnificence of a book that it could bring a reader to be drowned within his or her mind for a little while. Visual is the main sensory that readers may use as they read this poem. Obviously, readers will happen to witness things in their mind as they read the words that are contained in the poem, for example; when readers hear the word frigate there must be a shadow of a warship projected in their mind. It was then later discovered if Emily Dickinson did choose a frigate instead of a ship for a purpose. The poem itself was written in 1873 when the civil war just ended years behind.

Poems and proses produced during the Romantic period embody the essence of a nation struggling with different ideologies and working toward a national identity. While some works of literature were a reaction to the political and social conditions of the times, others embodied some of the following elements central to American Romanticism: the belief in the natural goodness of man, a delight in self-reflection, a yearning for solitude, a return to nature for spirituality, a focus on democracy and individual freedom, an emphasis on physicality and the beautiful development of new forms. The Romantic era is an expansive time period rife with social changes, economic development, political struggle, and technological development. Although it is considered part of American Romanticism, these subgenres often exhibit other

characteristics. Now we can see some characteristics in more detail and analyze some examples from Romantic poetry and prose:

Characteristic 1: Emotion-The Romanticists were deeply in touch with their feelings. Emotion was one of the most crucial characteristics of the Romantic period. Romanticists cared about emotions such as fear, awe, and horror. In stories written by Romantic writers, characters often focus on the more sentimental sides of the story, including their inner struggles, dreams, and passions. Many characters in Romantic literature fell in love and wrote about death and the human relationship with god to tie the romanticism with philosophy and religion. One remarkable sample “Because I could not stop for death” by Emily Dickinson:

*Because I could not stop for Death –
He kindly stopped for me –
The Carriage held but just Ourselves –
And Immortality*⁶⁸

It is vividly noticeable that the speaker is facing the inevitability of death from the very first stanza. The speaker saying that she “could not stop for Death” shows she had not necessarily planned to die--but Death came for them anyway. If we pay attention to the meaning of “stopped” in the poem, we can see a better idea of how the speaker was feeling about the inevitability of Death’s approach. “Stopped” can depict “picked up” or “collected” in the context of the poem—at least when referring to Death stopping for the speaker. In other words, “stopped” doesn’t mean that Death halted its pursuit of the speaker to search for another mortal. In fact it means that Death is making a stop to pick her up, like a taxi or bus. In the poem speaker’s passion was described as the type of powerful emotion that was characteristic of Romantic literature.

Characteristic 2: An Awe of Nature-The Romanticists saw nature as a source of beauty and truth. Much of Romantic literature focuses on nature as something sublime. There are countless Romantic poets who wrote lyrical ballads about everything from birds and flowers to mountains and clouds. The following examples reveal the ideas given above., A Bird, came down the walk” by Emily Dickinson is an amazing nature poem which focuses on the actions of a bird going about its everyday life. In the poem, a speaker's seemingly everyday encounter with a bird leads to thoughts about the frightening side of nature—as well as nature's beauty. Under this speaker's watchful eye, the bird is at once a merciless predator, an anxious and vulnerable animal, and a lovely spark of life.

⁶⁸ Dickinson Emily, *The Complete Poems of Emily Dickinson*. / Ed. by Thomas Johnson. Boston; Toronto; Little, Browne and Company, 1960

Characteristic 3: The Idealization of Women- In the Romantic era, women were seen as innocent, pure creatures who should be admired and respected. Many Romantic poets and novelists centered their narratives around celebrating the purity and beauty of a woman. Unfortunately, this idealization meant that the Romantic Movement typically saw women as objects for male admiration rather than as people with their own dreams and ambitions. One example of the idealization of women is Edgar Allan Poe’s poem “Annabel Lee”:

*For the moon never beams, without bringing me dreams
Of the beautiful Annabel Lee;
And the stars never rise, but I feel the bright eyes
Of the beautiful Annabel Lee;
And so, all the night-tide, I lie down by the side
Of my darling—my darling—my life and my bride,
In her sepulchre there by the sea—
In her tomb by the sounding sea.⁶⁹*

The poet dreams of Annabel Lee and sees the brightness of her eyes in the stars. The narrator lies down by her side in her tomb by the sea at every night. Here, Poe puts Annabel on a pedestal as he describes how beautiful she was before her death.

Characteristic 4: The Celebration of the Individual-Many Romanticists saw themselves as self-reliant, independent individuals who stood apart from the rest of society, and some even chose to lead largely isolated, solitary lives. Ralph Waldo Emerson wrote an essay called Self-Reliance in 1841, describing the importance of determining his own path and relying on his own resources. One well-known quote from the essay reads: "To be yourself in a world that is constantly trying to make you something else is the greatest accomplishment." In general, Romanticism believed that the content of literature should come from the writer’s imagination, with minimal outside input. Being derivative, or copying work that had come before, was seen as the worst sin. Walt Whitman took this a step farther by writing poetry in free verse, without any rhyme or meter. This is common in poetry today, but at the time, it was a groundbreaking choice that shook off previous rules. Here’s Walt Whitman’s famous poem “Song of Myself” in free verse:

*For every atom belonging to me as good belongs to you.
I loafe and invite my soul,
I lean and loafe at my ease observing a spear of summer grass.
My tongue, every atom of my blood, form’d from this soil, this air,
Born here of parents born here from parents the same, and their parents the same,
I, now thirty-seven years old in perfect health begin,*

⁶⁹ Poe, Edgar Allan. The Complete Poetry of Edgar Allan Poe. New York City: New American Library, 2008

Hoping to cease not till death.

Creeds and schools in abeyance,

Retiring back a while sufficed at what they are, but never forgotten,

I harbor for good or bad, I permit to speak at every hazard,

Nature without check with original energy.

In the given poem, we can notice how he doesn't conform to any type of rhyme scheme or meter. Instead, he writes a poem that feels almost like a conversation. Robert Bleil sees the poet as a person of celebration “if his British contemporary Alfred Lord Tennyson is the national poet of mourning, then Whitman is the national poet of celebration”⁷⁰ Whitman's Song of Myself can be considered an adventure of seeking identity. In every situation, incident or experience we find Whitman is seeking his identity. Through the going process of poem we find him creating a relation between him and the reader. He focuses in the process of celebrating himself. But he does not focus only his limited self but his inner self also. To Whitman one has to identify his self. Without the self-realization the ultimate quest of life can not be ended where the identity of God is supposed to be revealed and the real satisfaction is supposed to be gained. The quest for divine unity is a mystic journey. To Whitman either of body and soul must not be abased regarding to the other. Each one has to get equal importance and the role of both should be celebrated to achieve the ultimate satisfaction.

Characteristic 6: Spirituality and the Occult-Romanticists were interested in the infinite and the divine. As a result, Romanticism began to include occult and supernatural elements. Many Romantic poems and stories involve some aspect of the mystical or the “gothic. Edgar Allan Poe is a commonly cited example of a Romantic writer who used spiritual and supernatural elements in his stories and poems. This is a verse from his poem “Spirits of the Dead” (1827), which depicts a divine mystery:

The breeze—the breath of God—is still—

And the mist upon the hill,

Shadowy—shadowy—yet unbroken,

Is a symbol and a token—

How it hangs upon the trees,

A mystery of mysteries!

The mysterious poem illustrates the intersections of gothic horror and romance, depicting beauty in both life and in death, and supporting Poe's belief in seeing man and Nature holistically, rather than isolated sections. Although it attracted very little attention of publication, it has contributed to Poe's legacy and high regard as a prolific and influential writer and poet. This poem's gothic imagery, the

⁷⁰ American Literatures After 1865 Copyright © by Scott D. Peterson; Amy Berke; Robert Bleil; Jordan Cofer.p-35

personification of nature, and the immersion into mystery and beauty depicts the nuances and intersections of death and beauty.⁷¹

Conclusion

American Romanticism in poetry was a multifaceted movement that celebrated the individual, reveled in the beauty of nature, and challenged societal conventions. Through emotive verses and introspective narratives, Romantic poets captured the essence of the human experience, leaving an indelible mark on American literature. This paper has attempted to find out and then explain the major contributions American Romantic poets and their exploration of emotion, nature, and spirituality continues to resonate with readers, offering timeless insights into the human condition.

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⁷¹ Arthur Hobson Quinn, Edgar Allan Poe: A Critical Biography (1941)